

AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF LAMINATION RESIDUAL STRAIN
AND STRESS IN COMPOSITE DURING FABRICATION

Song Huan-cheng Li Jian-xin
Beijing Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Beijing, China

ABSTRACT

The T_g of the 90° specimens of the UDC measured by DMA was taken as stress-free temperature in the present work. The thermal strains of the UDC and symmetric cross-ply laminate (SCPL) made of fiber glass / 648 epoxy were measured by means of embedded strain gages. Experimental results were treated by the classical lamination theory, and it has been shown that the analytical predictions were in good agreement with the experimental data, as well as that differences between the lamination residual stresses (LRSes) in composite and the LRSes in composite during fabrication should be distinguished.

INTRODUCTION

As one of the intrinsic characteristics of composite materials, fabrication residual stresses (FRSes) are closely related to the components, structures and fabrication process of the materials. When the components and the structures are specified, the influence of fabrication process upon residual stresses (RSes) will be dominant. Thus, the magnitude of the RSes reflects the suitability of the selection of fabrication process conditions. The strength, dimensional stability and structural integrity of composite will be influenced by the existence of prestresses or FRSes. If the composites were over prestressed, cracks or crazings will be inevitably initiated. Thus, the design, fabrication and application of composite materials need to know of the FRSes developed during the curing process.

During the last decade, much efforts, either analytically, or experimentally, were made to evaluate the FRSes (curing stresses or LRSes). [1]-[4] Detailed knowledge of composite materials and fabrication conditions is necessary to investigate the problem. In the present work the stress-free temperature will be discussed and experimentally determined. Due to the lack of effective methods, only the cooling process of the cured composite materials has been studied.

STRESS-FREE TEMPERATURE

The stress relaxation capability in transverse direction signifi-

cantly influence the magnitude of LRSes. The contribution of chemical shrinkage to LRSes and the relaxation behavior are related to the mechanical state of the matrix. When the mechanical state transition takes place, the material exhibits stress relaxation rate higher than the two neighboring states, therefore the RSEs cannot accumulate easily and the pre-accumulated RSEs are relaxed substantially. The transition involved in the system discussed is glass transition. Glass transition temperature characterize the essence of stress relaxation better. So it is taken as stress-free temperature. It is not certainly the cure temperature of the system and different from the stress-free temperature defined by H.T. Hahn. [3] The measurement of stress-free temperature is also different. The dynamic mechanical analysis method was employed in the present work. The temperature at which the loss of modulus of 90° specimen reaches its maximum is taken as T_g , i.e. stress-free temperature. Observation of the record curves of high temperature static tension experiments of 90° specimen shows that around the T_g determined above, the area of load-strain retardation loops reach its maximum. The greatest degree of stress relaxation at T_g is therefore proved.

Figure 1. DMA curve of 90° specimen of fiber-glass/648 novolak composite.

The dynamic modulus-temperature spectra of 90° specimen is shown in Fig. 1. The stress-free temperature determined from the spectra is 430°K, which is lower than the curing temperature of the system, 443°K.

CALCULATION OF LAMINATION RESIDUAL STRAINS

When the temperature is higher than the stress-free temperature, the lamination residual strains could be calculated, but the corresponding RSEs relax rapidly, so it is negligible compared with the RSEs developed in the material at room temperature. Below the stress-free temperature, the mechanical properties in the transverse direction may be considered linear elastic, the LRSes due to the cooling of the material will no longer relax. So that stress-free temperature is taken as the initial point for the calculation of lamination residual strains that the LRSes correspond.

The thermal strains of UDC at constraint-free state are taken as references for the calculation of lamination residual strains in the laminate. The structure of the laminate discussed here is $[0/90]_3$.

The lamina residual strains in the SCPL are:

$$\varepsilon_{RS}^0 = \varepsilon_{c-p}^0 - \varepsilon_f^0 \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_{RS}^{90} = \varepsilon_{c-p}^{90} - \varepsilon_f^{90} \quad (2)$$

where ε_f^0 , ε_f^{90} are respectively the free thermal strains in the 0° and 90° directions of UDC at constraint-free state cooled from stress-free temperature to a certain temperature T . ε_{c-p}^0 , ε_{c-p}^{90} are the on-axis strains of the lamina in the laminate at constrained or constraint-free state for the same temperature change. For the laminate discussed here, $\varepsilon_{c-p}^0 = \varepsilon_{c-p}^{90}$. ε_{c-p} at constraint-free state can be predicted from from ε_f^0 and ε_f^{90} by CIT. The theoretical values of residual strains are obtained if the theoretical values of ε_{c-p} are used in eqn. 1 and 2.

The strain gages embedded in the laminate were employed to measure ε_f^0 , ε_f^{90} and ε_{c-p} . This technique has its special advantages when ε_{c-p} at constrained state is to be measured. The strain gages used are self-compensated short-joint strain gages for 0° direction of CF/epoxy composite. The technique is simplified due to the selection of strain gage.

EXPERIMENTS

1. Materials Selected

The matrix is 648 Novolak, cured with 3% $BF_3 \cdot MEA$. It is reinforced by 2# high strength fiber glass. The configurations of the laminates are $\{0/90\}_{3S}$ and $\{0\}_{12}$. The strain gages are placed at the mid of the middle plane of the pre-preg laminate. The filter paper was used as resin absorber.

2. Material Preparation

The materials were prepared by mold press method. The cross-SCPL and UDC were cured in one mold. The cure schedule was:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} \text{r. t.} & \xrightarrow{1^\circ\text{K/min}} & 363^\circ\text{K} & \xrightarrow{40\text{min}} & 363^\circ\text{K} & \xrightarrow{1^\circ\text{K/min}} & 413^\circ\text{K} & \xrightarrow{1\text{hr}} \\ & & & & & & & \\ & & 413^\circ\text{K} & \xrightarrow{0.5^\circ\text{K/min}} & 443^\circ\text{K} & \xrightarrow{3\text{hr}} & 443^\circ\text{K} & \xrightarrow{1^\circ\text{K/min}} & \text{r. t.} \end{array}$$

The temperature for the application of pressure was 388°K . The Pressure kept during the cooling process was 0.49GPa. The FVR is 65%. Fig.1 shows that the materials were cured completely.

The outputs of the embedded strain gages were recorded during the cooling process. The ε_f^0 , ε_f^{90} and ε_{c-p} at constraint-free state are measured from the same laminate placed in the oven.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The on axis thermal strains of the laminate at constrained or constraint-free state during the cooling process.

Figure 2. The thermal strain curves of UDC and SCPL during cooling.

1,2: 0° direction of UDC. 1,f. 2,m.
 3,4: on-axis direction of SCPL. 3,f. 4,m.
 5,6: 90° direction of UDC. 5,f. 6,m.
 f: measured at constraint-free state in the oven.
 m: measured at constrained state in the mold.

It is shown in Fig. 2 that the differences between the true values of thermal strains of the laminates at constraint-free state and those at the constrained state are significant. Since the thermomechanical properties of the resin absorber, mold and the laminates are different, at the edges of the specimens embedded with strain gages, the resin squeezed out from the laminate being cured became a constraint to the free deformations of the specimens and the resin absorber. Although there was no chemical adhesion between the porous Teflon layer and the resin absorber or the laminates, there was obvious static electric charge action between them. Therefore the constraints from the resin absorber and Teflon layer can't be eliminated easily and the influences of the constraints are related to the materials and their thicknesses selected. Although measures were taken to reduced the influences from the mold in the experiment, it is not sure that the influences were completely eliminated. If the constraint from the mold is not negligible, the results measured from mold press system are not the same as those from autoclave system. Therefore, the curve 2, curve 4 and curve 6 in Fig. 2 are the coordinative results of the mold, assisting materials and the laminates.

2. The constraint exerted on the laminates

The strain difference-temperature curves shown in Fig. 3 were obtained from the differences between the thermal strains of the laminates constrained by the mold and assisting materials and the thermal strains of the laminates at constraint-free state shown in Fig. 2. The constraints indicated by the differences are related to the change of temperature and the materials involved.

The values in curve 1 and those in curve 3 for the same temperature

Figure 3. Strain difference-temperature curves of the laminates during cooling.
 1: 0° direction of UDC
 2: on-axis direction of the SCPL
 3: 90° direction of UDC

in Fig.3 were used to obtain the constraint stress components in the UDC. Taking the SCPL as a quasi-isotropic integrity, curve 2 was also treated with CLT to obtain the average values of constraint stresses exerted on the SCPL in the mold. The results were shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. The average constraint stress component-temperature curves of the laminates.
 1: 90° direction of UDC
 2: 0° direction of UDC
 3: on-axis direction of the lamina in the SCPL

It is shown in Fig. 4 that the constraint stresses increase with the decrease of temperature in a general trend. The smaller the coefficients of thermal expansion in a certain direction of the materials, the larger the constraint compression stress in the direction.

Because of the largest change of thermal expansion coefficient exhibited in the 90° direction of the UDC, the general trend shown in 90° direction was slightly different from the trend in 0° direction of the UDC or the on-axis direction of a SCPL. It is deduced from the discussion above that the constraint stresses are structural thermal stresses at a higher level. They can't be neglected as compared with

the SCPL at constraint-free state. Therefore the thermal strain outputs of the UDC in the mold are not the suitable references for the calculation of the RSEs of constrained laminate at a lamina level. The outputs at constraint-free state should be used.

3. The comparison between the theoretical and experimental values of thermal strains in the on-axis direction of SCPL.

Figure 5. The comparison between experimental data and theoretical values of the thermal strains of the SCPL.

- 1,3: experimental data
- 2,4: theoretical values
- 1,2: at constrained state
- 3,4: at constraint-free state

Figure 6. The comparison between experimental data and theoretical values of the thermal strains of the SCPL.

- 1,3: experimental data
- 2,4: theoretical values
- 1,2: at constrained state
- 3,4: at constraint-free state

Curve 2,4, in Fig. 5 are the thermal strain curves of SCPL evaluated by CLT, taking 443°K as the initial temperature for the calculation. The average error between curve 4 and curve 3 per 100°K was 1.6%. The curve resulted from the thermal strains of UDC in the mold agreed surprisingly well with the experimentally measured thermal strains of SCPL

in the mold.

The stress-free temperature determined in the present work was taken as the initial temperature for the calculation in Fig.6. The average error between curve 4 and curve 3 per 100°K was 5.1% and that between curve 2 and curve 1 was 5.7%.

Generally speaking, both methods satisfactorily predicted the thermal strain behavior of the SCPL. Taking stress-free temperature as the initial temperature for the calculation, the results can be more reasonable. The agreement between curve 2 and curve 1 is explained as the constraints of the same mechanism were exerted on UDC and the SCPL. The constraint in 0° and 90° direction can be "laminated" as the constraint exerted on the SCPL. If the integrity between the laminates and the assisting materials exist (the assisting materials do not crack) the differences between curve 2 and curve 1 cannot be great. Because of the good agreement between the experimental and theoretical values, if the thermal strains of the UDCs at the two states are obtained, the thermal strains and the residual strains of the SCPLs to be obtained at the corresponding states can be evaluated by CLT and the good agreement between theoretical values and experimental data is consequential.

4. The on-axis lamination residual strains of a lamina in the SCPL In Fig.7 and Fig. 8, the on-axis lamination residual strains of a lamina in the SCPL were calculated with 430°K as stress-free temperature; the thermal strains of UDC at constraint-free state were taken as the references for the calculation.

Figure 7. Residual strain-temperature curves in the 0° direction of a lamina in the SCPL.

Figure 8. Residual strain-temperature curves in the 90° direction of a lamina in the SCPL.

Curve 1, curve 2 are the lamination residual strains calculated

by eqn. 1 and 2 using the experimental data of thermal strains of the SCPLs at constraint-free state. Whereas curve 6 and 5 are the corresponding results using the theoretical values. As is explained above, good agreements between curve 2 and 6, curve 1 and 5 exist. The residual strains calculated in this way are the lamination residual strains of the angle-ply laminate in common sense.

Curve 4 and 3 are the lamination residual strains calculated by eqn. 1 and 2 using the experimental data of thermal strains of the SCPLs in the mold. The differences between curve 4 and 2, curve 3 and 1 are apparent. The differences are caused by the constraint exerted on the SCPL. Because the constraint stresses are compressive, the residual strains in 0° direction are larger, therefore curve is under curve 1. Curve 4 is under curve 2 for similar reason. The residual strains calculated thus characterize the lamination residual strain during the fabrication of the SCPLs on the prescribed references, which include the combination action of the mold, assisting materials and other factors on the laminates and are different from the lamination residual strains of a produced laminate. The difference calls attention for the measurement and evaluation of residual strains of laminates.

5. The on-axis LRSes of a lamina in the SCPLs

Figure 9. LRS-temperature curves in the on-axis direction of a lamina in the SCPL.

Fig. 9 shows the on-axis LRSes obtained from the CLT using the residual strain curves shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

Curve 1,2,3,4,5,6 are LRSes--temperature curves corresponding to curve 1,2,3,4,5,6 in Fig. 7, Fig. 8 respectively. It is easily understood that curve 1,2 are close to curve 5,6 respectively. Curve 1 and 2 are approximately symmetrical with respect to T-axis, as is hold for curve 5 and 6. The general tendency of the curves can be explained by CLT. They are the LRS es of the produced laminate.

The T-axis is not the symmetric axis for curve 3 and 4, because the free thermal expansion of the SCPL is confined. Because of the compressive constraint stresses on the SCPL. The curves are shifted downward, therefore curve 3 is under curve 1 and 5, curve 4 is under curve 2 and curve 6. The LRSes in the present case are different from the LRSes in a produced composite laminates. For distinction, they are

named as fabrication RSEs.

In general, the fundamental data are measured on UDC at constraint-free state which is taken as references for most calculations. Seldom is UDC at constrained state taken as references. The concept proposed not only better characterizes the stress states in the angle-ply laminate during fabrication, it is also convenient to the evaluation of the influences of RSEs on the materials based upon the fundamental properties of UDC at constraint-free state.

It is shown in Fig. 9 that the LRSes change with temperature. Although the stress-free temperature lower than the curing temperature is adopted to lower the predicted values of the LRSes, the LRS at room temperature range can not be neglected, compared with the transverse strength.

It is shown in this paper that the assisting materials and the mold material have significant influence on the LRSes in the laminate. The selection of assisting materials and the mold materials is not arbitrary, it gives opportunity for the control of RSEs during curing process.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The strain gage embedment method is effective for the study of LRSes during cooling. Good agreement between experimental data and theoretical evaluation can be achieved.
2. The embeded strain gage has unique advantage to reveal the influence of the mold and the assisting materials on the thermal strains, lamination residual strains and LRSes of the Laminates. The constraint is thermoelastic, it can not be neglected as compared with the magnitude of the LRSes.
3. The selection of reference states shows that the LRSes in a produced constraint-free SCPL are different from the LRSes in the SCPL during the cooling process of the fabrication. The fabrication residual stresses are used for distinction.
4. The stress-free temperature used in the present work can be easily measured, which has definite implication related to material properties. More reasonable results can be obtained when it is taken as initial temperature for the calculation.

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